

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Paul Whaley

Your email address: paul@whaleyresearch.uk

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 04/04/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, methodology, writing - review & editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

X	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
	From litigation or legal cases
	From grants
	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

X	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
X	Current and previous research findings or projects
X	Commitments to specific standards or processes
	Publicly held positions
	Personal relationships
X	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
X	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I receive an honorarium in my role as Editor-in-Chief of Evidence-Based Toxicology, the journal to which this manuscript is being submitted. EBT will be involved in the trial described in the manuscript. I do not expect any direct financial benefits from my involvement in this work, but developing effective workflows for improving publishing standards is part of my role as an editor of the journal.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am actively involved in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in research. I have developed conduct standards (e.g. COSTER), reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage) to support the production of high quality systematic reviews and evidence maps and to support the evaluation of research (PRIVAT, INVITES). I am an active member of the GRADE Working Group, an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy in the UK. I have a senior role at the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration that involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods, and open science practices, in toxicology and environmental health.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "P.A. Welch." The signature is written in a cursive, slightly slanted style.

Notes

(1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.

(2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.

(3) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.

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Your name: Brian A. Nosek

Your email address: nosek@cos.io

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 04/04/2024

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Conceptualization, funding acquisition, supervision, writing - review & editing

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I am an employee of the nonprofit Center for Open Science (COS) that has a mission to increase openness, integrity, and reproducibility of research. COS offers support to journals, editors, and researchers in adopting and conducting Registered Reports.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have a commitment to high-quality methods of review and am involved in a number of projects aimed at improving research standards.

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Your name: Noah A. Haber

Your email address: noah@cos.io

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 04/04/2024

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Conceptualization, methodology, project administration, writing - original draft, writing - review & editing

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Your name: Timothy M. Errington

Your email address: tim@cos.io

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 04/04/2024

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Your name: Macie Daley

Your email address: macie@cos.io

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 04/04/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Project administration, writing - review & editing

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